

**THE POSSIBILITIES OF EFFECTIVE USE OF ELECTRONIC
EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT
EDUCATION OF PUPILS**

Kunnazarov Ilesbay Sarsenbaevich

Independent researcher of Nukus State Pedagogical
institute named after Ajiniyaz

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Abstract. The article aims to present the process of using electronic educational resources for the organization of independent work of pupils. As a consequent, the article presents the possibilities of the use of new pedagogical mechanisms that contribute to the effective cognitive activity of pupils of vocational schools. It is shown that the possibilities of use of electronic educational resources help pupils to transfer their knowledge and solve their problem in conducting independent works. It is confirmed that the use of electronic educational resources in independent work benefits pupils in overcoming learning difficulties, contributes to the creation of comfortable conditions for closer and more productive interaction between teachers and pupils in the educational process.

Keywords: electronic educational resources, independent work, organization, pupils, possibilities.

Introduction. Modern socio-economic processes and the requirements of the post-industrial information society set new guidelines for the development and modernization of vocational schools, an important feature of which today is the shift of the vector of educational activity towards independent work. In the overall structure of the pupil's educational activity, the share of independent training during one semester accounts for up to 50% of the study time. Meanwhile, it is obvious that this time is often used quite irrationally. All this points to the need to organize independent work of pupils, which will allow to intensify and individualize the training of pupils.

It is known that during classroom work, the teacher is more active, and pupils perform a more or less passive role, while the highest degree of activity appears when organizing independent work of pupils. But not every "independent work" is essentially independent. Success can only be brought by one who is very well prepared by the teacher [4]. Therefore, it is important to consider how to organize independent work of pupils in the conditions of informatization of education so that they have both interest in work and satisfaction from the result. In this regard, it is necessary to consider the essence of the concept of

"independent work", the principles of the organization of independent activity of pupils.

G.E.Kovaleva notes that independence is, first of all, the independence of actions, thinking. The main condition for a sufficiently deep assimilation of the material is its analytical and synthetic processing, which consists in an independent analysis of new information, i.e. the allocation of basic concepts in it, the establishment of cause-effect relationships and relationships between them and, thus, understanding the educational material, and in general, determining the main and secondary in it. Only on the basis of such an understanding of the material can one independently reason, prove, generalize [6, p.21-22].

Thus, independence serves as a basis for independent cognitive activity. In the process of learning, pupils' independence is designed to ensure the implementation of one of the most important principles of vocational school pedagogy – the principle of consciousness, which emphasizes the undoubted importance of the problem of the formation of this quality in pupils. To understand the specifics of independent work, it is also necessary to disclose its main types.

Let's consider a kind of classification by the nature of cognitive activity proposed by I.I. Malkin, who distinguishes the following types of independent work:[4].

1. Works of reproductive type:

a) Reproducing. The performance of these works is based on the restoration of previously studied material in memory, which is necessary for understanding the new material.

b) Training. This type provides not only a simple reproduction of the studied material, but also the application of previously acquired knowledge in new situations.

c) Overview. These are tasks for the ordering and systematization of the studied information. Their use is advisable at the final stage of fixing the material.

d) Verification. Their goal is a comprehensive check of the quality of knowledge acquisition. When performing these tasks, pupils develop self-control skills. These skills are also important for the development of memory processes such as arbitrary reproduction.

2. Works of cognitive-search type:

a) Preparatory work. When performing them, pupils use the available information, while being convinced of the incompleteness of their knowledge on

the topic studied. This leads them to the need for a deeper acquaintance with the new material.

b) Ascertaining works. Such works are associated with the description of new factors and phenomena by their external signs: observations of natural phenomena and social life, the study of the didactic are educational tasks based on research methods of science, during which students identify essential features of concepts, establish cause-and-effect dependencies, “discover” laws, etc.

d) Logical search work. These include various tasks on operating with essential features of the studied concepts used at the final stage of presentation and consolidation.

3. Works of creative type:

a) artistic and figurative independent works. Creative works are understood as independent works, as a result of which pupils create something new, original.

b) Scientific and creative works. Independent work of this type includes educational activities that go not only beyond the curriculum, but also related to the solution of cognitive tasks of increased difficulty – the manifestation of one's own initiative, the search for an original solution, etc.

c) Structural and technical works. This type of work includes creative design, construction using special computer programs.

4 Works of cognitive and practical type:

a) Educational and practical work. These include the production of visual aids (graphs, diagrams, diagrams, device layouts, preparation of articles for school newspapers, magazines, etc.).

b) Social and practical independent work. This refers to educational activities that go beyond academic life.

The main feature of electronic educational resources is the possibility of free independent choice and the possibility of interaction with the object of learning - interactivity. This ensures mutual cooperation between the teacher and the pupil, in which electronic educational resources act as an intermediary or a common field of their joint work. The functions of the teacher are reduced to the organization of learning conditions, access to materials and tools, to consulting in case of difficulties, i.e. supervising the learning process. Electronic means of educational purposes are ICT tools used together in conjunction with educational, regulatory, technical, organizational and instructional materials that ensure the implementation of the optimal technology of their pedagogical use [7, p. 157-160].

The possibilities of effective use of electronic educational resources in independent work allow pupils to:

- organize various forms of activity of trainees for the independent extraction and presentation of knowledge;
- apply the capabilities of ICT in the process of performing various types of educational activities, including such as registration, collection, storage, processing of information, interactive dialogue, modeling of objects, phenomena, processes, working with virtual laboratories;
- check the intellectual capabilities of the trainees, the level of their knowledge, skills, skills, the level of preparation for a particular lesson;
- manage training, automate the processes of monitoring the results of educational activities, training, testing, generate tasks depending on the intellectual level of a particular student, the level of his knowledge, skills, skills, characteristics of his motivation
- create conditions for the implementation of independent educational multimedia, hypermedia, hypertext;
- manipulate information, modify the presented information according to different parameters, etc.

Conclusion. Taking above-mentioned data into account, it can be concluded that electronic educational resources are the possibility of free independent choice and the possibility of interaction with the object of learning - interactivity. This ensures mutual cooperation between the teacher and the pupil, in which electronic educational resources act as an intermediary or a common field of their joint work. The possibilities of the usage of electronic educational resources in independent learning are the organization of training, consulting and testing of an unlimited number of pupils through networks; combination of traditional pedagogical methods with the latest communication and multimedia technologies, effective interaction of teachers and pupils at a convenient time for everyone; independent preparation of pupils; testing and automatic assessment of knowledge; control of the organization of training and its effectiveness.

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